

Zoo-Ontologies: Materiality and Visuality in the Multispecies Tangle

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Abstract

This paper probes into the opportunities of the ontological critique for the archaeology of human-animal relationships. I argue that “ontological” is somewhat of a misnomer for this endeavour as the aim is not to promote a new “metaphysical” archaeology but instead to give way to radically empirical, yet conceptually-consequential, investigations concerned with uncovering archaeological pasts otherwise. I sketch out the deep-running bearing of the ontological critique for our apprehension of key concepts underpinning much archaeological research on human-animal relationships and take some first steps to “open up” the empirical record from entrenched presentist shackles. I suggest that materiality and visuality offer privileged optics to rethink both the animal and the human and how they attend to and co-make each other in deep prehistory, exploring some promising avenues of zoontological inquiry, including the impartiality, portability, and fluidity of nonhuman bodies and bodily qualities, the nature of animal-oriented tool-making, as well as the non-representationalisms of animal visualizations in the European Mesolithic and Palaeolithic. I point out that a preoccupation with the abstract rather than the literal often leads us astray and that cultivating our ability to trace and interpret such concreteness may greatly advance animal archaeologies.

Keywords: Ontology, epistemology, multispecies archaeology, human-animal relations, materiality, visuality, non-representational theory

39 **Situating the ontological critique as radical observation**

40 In March 2017, the *Whanganui* on the North Island of New Zealand (*Aotearoa*), was the first
41 river to officially receive the status as a legal person (Charpleix, 2018; Brierley *et al.*, 2019;
42 Kramm, 2020). For the Indigenous *Te Atihaunui-a-Paparangi* Māori, the river, whom they refer
43 to as *Te Awa Tupua*, is a living, breathing, and expansive entity “from the mountains to the sea”
44 (Charpleix, 2018), integral to their way of being and foundational to their self-understanding
45 and identity. Andean mountains have similarly been positioned as troubled “metapersons”
46 (Gose, 2018), and *Te Urewera*, a mostly forested and sparsely populated rugged hill area in
47 New Zealand which forms a key habitat for most of the country’s native forest-bird species,
48 was released from its National Park status in 2014 in order to recognize its *Ngāi Tūhoe* Māori
49 status as a living person (Sanders, 2018; Coombes, 2020). In April 2024, it was reported that
50 Māori and Pacific leaders have further granted legal personhood to whales because of their
51 ecological and cosmological significance to people in the region,¹ and heated discussions on
52 animal sentience and consciousness, re-sparked by the *New York Declaration on Animal*
53 *Consciousness* (Andrews *et al.*, 2024), are equally taken to have consequences for the expansion
54 of personhood to at least some candidate nonhumans (Corbey and Lanjouw, 2013; Korsgaard,
55 2016). The issues raised by these cases touch upon ontological questions,² i.e., how to organize,
56 define, and cut-off what is said to make up “nature”, and what can be claimed to exist, live,
57 possess agency, be endowed with subjectivity, personhood, and so forth. They also strike into
58 the heart of the humanities as what is put a stake here is the confident “extension” of key
59 qualities, capabilities, and status descriptions long regarded to set humans apart from other
60 entities and phenomena in the world including nonhuman animals.

61 These issues are both controversial and political not only because they tend to assume
62 that the antidote lies in the mere levelling of humanist³ categories across the human-nonhuman
63 divide (see esp. Wolfe, 2003), but also because they challenge and complicate notably Western⁴

¹ <https://www.abc.net.au/pacific/whales-given-legal-personhood-by-pacific-leaders/103681180>

² Recapitulating the state-of-the-art in debates about ontology in archaeology and anthropology is beyond the scope of this paper but relevant references are highlighted whenever necessary. Useful overviews of current debates on ontological matters of concern in both disciplines can be found for example in Henare, Holbraad and Wastell (2007), Kohn (2015), Heywood (2017), Ribeiro (2018), Alberti (2016), and Harris and Cipolla (2017a). Tsing (2018) contains useful material about the relationship between the widely proclaimed ontological turn and animal studies. The archaeological literature is particularly diverse and Preucel (2021) distinguishes at least three main approaches: symmetrical archaeology, assemblage thinking, and relational archaeologies.

³ Humanism is understood here as a historically-derived tradition of thinking, largely originating in Europe, centring humans (notably the idea of the *Anthropos*), emphasising and obsessing with specific characteristics such as rationality, language, and morality, and elevating the associated being above other forms of existence (see esp. Wolfe, 2003 and Salzani, 2017 for foundational discussions; cf. Hussain, 2025 for animal archaeologies).

⁴ The notion of the “West” – or “Western” – is used not in an ontological sense here, but as an empirical descriptor of a specific historical formation of action and thought and a category of self-identification, cultural identity, and demarcation. What the West *is* remains contested and is subject to constant (re)negotiation, and some have argued that it is precisely this vagueness from which the idea draws its appeal and political potency. Said (1978) famously showed how ideas about Westernness created the foil for the “Orient”, and there is a rich literature on the relationship between the idea of the West and the social and political projects of modernity (Appadurai, 2010), often linked to landmark developments in Europe such as the accelerating scientification of life since the 17th century (Hasse, 2021), the rise of capitalism as “second nature” (Moore, 2016b), and the polarization of the world in colonizers and colonized in the age of imperialism and colonialism, creating the “West” as a powerful historical category within the world system of the 18th, 19th, 20th and early 21st centuries (see already Wallerstein, 1992). Following Sahlins (2022), and to some extent Assmann (2015, 2018), Western configurations of thought and action are rooted in the Axial Age and exemplify a particular strand of being within “cultures of transcendence”. The point is that the West can be mapped on various coordinates of recent history, including the Cold War period, but it cannot be reduced to any of them; this is because, importantly, the West is above all an imaginary, it is based on an “imagined community” (Anderson, 2016) and it rests on particular visions of one’s place in history and one’s relationship to the past (cf. Geroulanos, 2024). The West, as understood here, stands above all for a situated lens of how a particular group of people has come to look at, interact with, and appropriate the world (both materially

64 apprehensions of reality and are deeply embedded in ongoing power struggles about the kind
65 of worlds we wish to inhabit, foster, and promulgate (Goldman, Nadasdy and Turner, 2011;
66 Blaser, 2013; Cadena and Blaser, 2018). Indigenous positionalities are increasingly drawn upon
67 to encourage and support nature protection and biodiversity conservation initiatives, for
68 example, and such framings have not only earned enthusiasm, acclaim, and celebration, as
69 many Indigenous people do not neatly distinguish between “nature” and “culture” (e.g.,
70 Salmón, 2000; Descola, 2005; TallBear, 2011; Todd, 2014; Country *et al.*, 2015; Tallbear and
71 Willey, 2019; Kimmerer, 2021) and they should thus not be instrumentalized to re-inscribe the
72 very same logics responsible for the planetary polycrisis we find ourselves in. As part of a
73 poignant critique on the now commonplace tendency to force efforts of promoting Indigenous
74 sovereignty into the rationality and logics of the state (Nadasdy, 2017), Nadasdy (2016) has
75 argued that notions of citizenship cannot neatly be transferred between northern First Nations
76 and the Canadian state, especially not with regard to aspirations of “animal citizenship” as
77 influentially proposed by Donaldson and Kymlicka (2013). Such equalization shoehorns the
78 specificity of Indigenous practices and knowledges, re-formulating and thus misappropriating
79 their way of life within the normative coordinates of Western liberalism. The inversion of such
80 tropes, for example advocated by Weber’s *Indigenus* [ger. *Indigenialität*] (2018), pleading for
81 the rediscovery of the “savage in us” to cultivate much-needed “arts of ecological life”, is
82 equally problematic. These examples showcase the omnipresence of what has been referred to
83 as the “ontopolitics” of contemporary discourses on the Anthropocene, our own future, and the
84 future of the planet (Chandler, 2018). They illustrate the trouble with engaging the ontological:
85 to take ontologies seriously and to work with them requires more than merely inverting the
86 Western metaphysical relationship between ontology and epistemology, it demands to unclasp
87 them both as products of situated world engagement, belabouring them as humanist registers of
88 theory forwarding ideas such as, e.g., “citizenship” or “agency” (Wolfe, 2003).

89 To clarify this contestation, we thus need to return to some basic ideas of Western
90 humanism. Tylorian anthropology set out to explain cultural diversity by proposing that
91 peoples’ worldviews reflect their attempts, often unsuccessful, to make sense of and properly
92 explain the world, notably phenomena at first seemingly eluding human understanding. For
93 Tylor (1871), “religion” in the broadest sense was therefore a quality of “primitive” culture,
94 eventually to be superseded by rational science. Tylor’s “animism” sought to account for the
95 simplest – and thus most “primitive” – form this could take, anthropomorphizing other beings
96 such as animals, plants, and even stones by attributing a “spirit” or “soul” to them. His fellow
97 anthropologists continued to belabour this basic problem of the development of human society,
98 and other concepts such as “magic” (e.g. Douglas, 1992) were developed to specify the inferior
99 ways in which non-Western people tried to temper with the world (cf. Bird-David, 1999; and
100 see e.g. Heywood, 2017 for a discussion). In this rendering of anthropological difference,
101 cultural diversity was mere *surface difference* – fundamentally a question of *knowing* the world
102 rather than how the world truly *is*, thus recapitulating the orthodox understanding of the
103 relationship between ontology and epistemology: all humans inhabit the same world made up
104 by the same stuff (ontology or what there is) but come to know it in different ways
105 (epistemology or how we attain knowledge). This core tenet was not only taken to imply that
106 the human sciences have little to say about ontology as they can only study how humans see
107 the world and render it meaningful, it was also codified in the analytical distinction of “emic”

and intellectually), it is the scaffold for what has been called “coloniality of knowledge” (e.g., Shepherd, 2020), and has naturalized, and thus withdrawn from critical scrutiny, what has been identified as the “Western gaze” (e.g., Bhabha, 2004; Fanon, 2008). All of this does not imply, of course, that the category of the West is useful for negotiating a better, more inclusive, more diverse, just, and more cosmopolitan future, and many have argued it is probably not (illustrated by the ongoing genocide in Gaza in front of the world’s eyes: see e.g., Segal, 2025). This is because theorizing the West, I argue, leads us to draw attention to worlds otherwise.

108 vs. “etic” (Headland *et al.*, 1990), initially developed in linguistics (Pike, 1967) and then widely
109 referenced in anthropology and archaeology (Harris, 1976; Boissinot, 2015). Only an etic
110 perspective, in this view, can aspire to lay hands on the ontology of the world; emic accounts,
111 the primary domain of much social and cultural anthropology, dislodge of ontic claims (see
112 paradigmatically e.g., Geertz, 1973, 1984; see Kohn, 2015 for a critique). Anthropology’s
113 discomfort with this interpretation of the relationship between ontology and epistemology is
114 clearly reflected in recent attempts to move beyond what may be called “one-world
115 anthropology” to a dedicated anthropology of many worlds (e.g., Alberti and Marshall, 2009;
116 Alberti *et al.*, 2011; Cadena and Blaser, 2018), pivoted as a rich and possibly unexhaustive
117 “pluriverse” of variegated ways of being and becoming human (Blaser, 2013).⁵ Such proposals
118 undercut the idea of ontological monism deeply entrenched in Western thought.

119 The burden of this tension between ontology and epistemology weighs heavily on the
120 politics of difference, and thus how we make sense and position the situatedness and
121 incongruence of human life across space and time. Some have in response suggested to reframe
122 the problem of humanity entirely in order to foreground the “common ground” of being human,
123 shared commonalities that define us as planetary beings rather than emphasizing the situated
124 local in sight of the global (Antweiler, 2016). Such work is important as it shields against some
125 of the risks of overstating anthropological otherness and disconnectedness, yet it also risks to
126 abet the resurgence of universalist reasoning and naïve reinvigorations of the *Anthropos* (the
127 generic Adamian human as conjured in ancient Greek philosophical thinking: e.g., Wirth, 2022),
128 which much recent work in the humanities has sought to overthrow (Chakrabarty, 2009;
129 Haraway, 2016; Bajohr, 2020). Without buying into some of the problematic assumptions here,
130 human life, as many other forms of life, can be defined as *unified in its diversity*. The
131 qualification of commonalities and differences becomes then two sides of the same problem,
132 but none of the two can be cannibalized by, or subsumed under, the other. This also means that,
133 importantly, the problematic of the Anthropocene does not make away with questions of
134 diversity, to the contrary, it showcases that human Earth system agency throws human
135 differences, inequalities, and discordances into sharp relief. The Anthropocene is the product of
136 the actions and aspirations of a relative few and its evolution is in fact deepening all sorts of
137 intra-human differences while producing a whole barrage of novel disunities (e.g., Haraway,
138 2015; Moore, 2016a; Stöcker, 2024; Mbembe, 2025). Grappling with its many crises vividly
139 showcases that sustainable “solutions” will require affirmation and engagement with *human*
140 *difference* more than ever – to paraphrase Stuart Hall (1993); acknowledging and negotiating
141 difference as well as generatively living *with* and *across* difference presents one of the
142 overriding challenges of our time (Haraway, 2016; Fincher, Rose and Gibson, 2020).

143 The ontological critique must be placed into this wider context, contending that
144 difference requires careful retheorization because framing cultural diversity as mere surface
145 difference misconstrues the problem and is dangerous. Difference is pervasive and a
146 fundamental category of existence, so that questions of what there is cannot be separated from
147 how we act in and come to know the world. It is not enough, therefore, to say that culture is
148 variable while nature is not, as this simply embanks the politics of difference rather than
149 allowing for productive interrogations of what difference *is* and how it is *produced* across varied
150 contexts. As Viveiros de Castro (1998; 2016) has lucidly argued, Amerindian Indigenous
151 realities are based on the recognition that bodies are changeable, mutable, and varied, while
152 mentalities are essentially of a similar kind and thus transcend bodily differences. This inverts
153 the logic of Western polarities of mind vs. body and nature vs. culture: humans and animals

⁵ Nadasdy (2021) points out some of the issues, pitfalls, and conceptual difficulties that come with this “multiple-worlds thesis” and argues that rather than home in on multiple irreconcilable worlds, theoretical attention should be directed to the indeterminacy of the world and the associated anti-colonial politics.

154 share culture but not biology, culture is universal, biology is not. Natures are multiple and varied
155 in this optic, while culture is a commonality. The world is inhabited by different kinds of beings
156 who make sense of reality from distinct corporeal vantage points, animals also see themselves
157 as “humans” with “societies” and “material cultures” as part of their manifest form
158 (externalities), and humans are seen as “animals” (cf. Descola, 2005, 2021; Castro, 2016; see
159 Hill, 2019 and Laguens, 2024 for archaeological implications and applications). Stones can
160 equally become persons as people and stones interact in varied but often potent ways (Weedman
161 Arthur, 2017) and human “personhood” frequently turns out to be relational (Fowler, 2004;
162 Harrison-Buck and Hendon, 2018) or “extended”, challenging notions of self-containedness,
163 discreteness, and boundedness as well as the universal correspondence of personhood and
164 bodily identity. González-Ruibal and colleagues (2011), for example, have shown how the
165 production and utilization of arrowheads is inextricably woven into how the Awá of the
166 Brazilian Amazon construct and negotiate particular male selves, complicating the
167 interpretation of such artefacts as either utilitarian/functional or symbolic – not to speak of the
168 assumed exhaustiveness of the explanatory space problematically framed in this way. In reality,
169 the functional-symbolic binary presents itself as yet another interpretation of received but
170 situated ontology-epistemology hierarchies: “functional” is understood as that which elicits
171 causal effects through the ontological fabric of the world and thus reveals this fabric, whereas
172 “symbolic” registers meaning-making processes to do with how people know and imagine the
173 world. In this logic, there can only be one ontology of the world, cast as human-independent,
174 and this world is fundamentally given – even though it is perhaps not fully accessible to human
175 knowing, it can in principle be discovered and instrumentalized. Ontology-epistemology
176 relationships are understood as *correspondence* and there can thus only be one “correct” or
177 “effective” (in terms of control and manipulation) way of mapping them.

178 Foregrounding ontological matters is hence not least a response to the long-standing
179 humanist tendency to regard culture foremostly as an epistemic artefact – an expression of how
180 we think about the world and coat it in signs and symbols rather than as a powerful source and
181 motivation of world-making itself. Received wisdom in most Western academic traditions, in
182 other words, is based on the presupposition that epistemological pluralism meets ontological
183 monism, without considering the dynamic relationship between epistemological and
184 ontological registers of being in the world. Taking this dynamic relationship seriously entails a
185 dedicated departure from thinking about knowledge as a mere *representation* of the world,
186 resonating with broader tendencies to align the ontological critique with post-representational
187 theories (Gell, 1998; Thrift, 2008; cf. Jones, 2017, 2021; Eriksen, 2022 for archaeology);
188 knowledge, then, is to be understood not as an “imprint” of some independent externalities but
189 as a *consequence* of particular ways of being-in, engaging with, and making worlds, to be
190 pluralized not in isolation but in tandem with human actions, aspirations, and wider projects of
191 life. The world is not just acted upon but *enacted*, and thus inseparable from whoever makes
192 and sustains it (“(multispecies) worlding”: e.g., Anderson and Harrison, 2016; Lorimer, 2025).
193 Such worlds are precisely the intersection of ontology and epistemology as they emerge from
194 performative actions and processes and their spatiotemporal unfoldings. The implication is that
195 ontology is not a given and simply “out there” to collect or discover as presumed by classical
196 Western metaphysics, but marks yet another *locus of difference*. To wit, the insistence on
197 ontology being more fundamental than, or even foundational of, epistemology, with
198 implications for what is more variable than the other, is merely to reveal a specific meta-
199 ontology – an ontology of ontology-epistemology relations. The ontological critique belabours
200 precisely those efforts which close off such variability, seeking to “open up” both ontology and
201 epistemology from their conceptual shackles (Heywood, 2017). The recent upsurge of debates
202 on ontology in anthropology and archaeology, I would argue, is therefore paradoxically much
203 less about ontology itself than they initially suggest. Ribeiro (2019) has rightly warned about

204 the risks of naturalizing and thereby reifying ontological debates to promote and justify new
205 forms of “metaphysical dogma”, and even though this risk is to be taken seriously, it
206 misrepresents the motivations and goals of the ontological turn.

207 To engage with ontology is not so much about pinpointing and developing an ontology
208 which better captures the “nature of things”, as such logic would merely re-inscribe what the
209 ontological critique set out to dismantle. Rather, to engage with ontology is to challenge the
210 notion that difference is a surface phenomenon and thus to advance novel ways to chart the
211 “depths” of difference as a fundamental and pervasive quality of past human life (ontology is
212 not merely a postmodern placeholder for culture: see e.g., Alberti, 2016). The goal, instead, is
213 to expedite ontology for *empirical* analysis, for example by means of investigating how humans
214 and nonhuman have precisely enacted each other in the past, how this impinged on, and thereby
215 fostered specific, ontological registers of being and becoming, and how traditional
216 archaeological schemes of interpretation informed by ontological monism, such as the
217 functional-symbolic binary, are often inadequate or at least limit our understanding of the
218 human past. The ontological critique, in other words, aims to foster the very possibility that
219 things in the past were *otherwise* and to subject ourselves and whatever we archaeologically
220 study to such critical scrutiny of this “Other”. The impetus is to overcome the long-standing
221 tendency to render human-world relations in the *abstract* rather than to take them seriously, and
222 hence *literally*, and to avoid implicit imposition and judgment through the themselves-situated
223 categories we rely on to describe and make sense of such relations. The talk of “opening up”
224 ontology for empirical analysis (see e.g., Alberti and Marshall, 2009; Alberti, 2014, 2016;
225 Heywood, 2017) is accordingly no empty talk, it means to make ourselves aware of the tyranny
226 of our own ontological framings and to make it an empirical question which ontological
227 registers are at play in any given situation or broader historical context. It compels us to
228 recognize ontology as a *derived* category of human life rather than something carved out *a*
229 *priori*. Ontologies, in this view, emerge as *downstream consequences* of how people interact
230 with their worlds and so enact them, what practices they employ, what other entities they engage
231 with, and what generally matters for the successful conduct of these lives.

232 Fundamentally, then, fanning out an “ontological lens” to the past must avoid containing
233 this past within our own ontological positionalities, and should thus be less concerned with the
234 questions it answers than with those it raises. In contrast to what Ribeiro (2019) seems to
235 suggest, ontological debates in archaeology are thus precisely concerned with a re-
236 perspectivation of the empirical record itself; they cannot be qualified as dispensing with this
237 record or advocate some sort of independent “reality” or its “representation”; the ontological
238 lens is therefore not about “speculation”, it seeks to proffer new means to “let the data speak”
239 against the limitations imposed by our disciplined modes of categorization, methodological
240 procedure, and interpretation. Ironically, the ontological critique in this manner unclasps an
241 empiricism that is *more radical* than even positivism could have imagined – an empiricism that
242 releases the ontological, and thereby strengthens observation itself, instead of being tamed,
243 enfeebled, and domesticated by whatever can count as an acceptable lens. Alberti (2023) has
244 described this as the tendency to “overdetermine” the past and its objects by our long-rehearsed
245 ways of looking at, ordering, and explicating them and the resulting need to promote “arts of
246 noticing” in order to “reveal the material consequences of concepts that show up precisely
247 because they are not ours”. Pétursdóttir (2017) has similarly warned of the domestication of
248 possibilities through overly disciplined routines of taking up, handling, and making-sense of
249 archaeological materials, which often curtail their capacity to reveal difference.

250 In the remainder of this paper, I draw and build on this understanding of ontology to
251 counter some creeping misunderstandings of the concept in the archaeological literature and to
252 explore some of its consequences for the study of past human-animal relationships. I suggest

253 that multispecies archaeologies can greatly benefit from the kind of onto-epistemological
254 opening sketched in the previous paragraphs. Multispecies archaeologies have been developed
255 in particular to overcome the Cartesian bind of dualisms and assumptions with regard to the
256 animal specifically and human-animal relationalities more generally (e.g., Hamilakis and
257 Overton, 2013; Overton, 2016; Boyd, 2017; Armstrong Oma, 2018; Hill, 2021; Chazin, 2024;
258 Hussain and Brusgaard, 2024; Whitridge and Hill, 2024; Mannermaa, 2025). These
259 archaeologies have repositioned the question of the animal and animal alterity within much
260 broader questions of difference and diversity (see esp. Hussain, 2024a, 2025a, in pressa, in
261 pressb). As such, it may be argued that the “animal turn” (Ritvo, 2007; Cederholm *et al.*, 2014)
262 and its archaeological articulations bring ontological issues into sharp relief (see e.g., Boyd,
263 2017), as traditional categories such as “natural” and “wild” as well as the various functional
264 typologies to talk about, examine, and qualify human-animal relationships are increasingly
265 critiqued as hampering understanding rather than advancing it (see e.g., Baker *et al.*, 2024;
266 Hussain, 2024b; Lynch and Kelty, 2025). What an animal *is* has become almost as contested as
267 what *kind* of relationships to pay attention to (Hussain, 2025a). Most importantly, scholars
268 increasingly realize that human-animal relationships cannot be adequately studied through a
269 static analytical grid, as they inscribe into and enact multispecies worlds comprising situated
270 humans and nonhumans and supporting diverse and sometimes unique forms of interaction (cf.
271 Norton, 2024). Neither supposedly innocent faunal remains nor animal-related material culture
272 can be assumed anymore to be sufficiently understood as mere representations of the functional
273 or symbolic domain. These categories are contested themselves and they often curtail rather
274 than enable insight into the diversity of past human-animal engagements – a circumstance
275 perhaps especially evident in scholarship on past animal-related visual worlds.

276 I attend to these critical issues and argue that zoo-ontology⁶ should be brought to the
277 centre of theory-building, debate, and data analysis in animal archaeologies. I explore this “zoo-
278 ontological” bearing through two interpretive optics: i) materiality; and ii) visibility. This initial
279 exploration speaks to general concerns and issues in the field but focuses in particular on
280 debates and preoccupations in deep-time archaeology, hence primarily mobilizing empirical
281 material from diverse Pleistocene and Holocene hunter-gatherer pasts and the human-animal
282 constellations they have fostered (see Warren, 2021 for the notion of hunter-gatherer
283 archaeology). I suggest taking the ontological critique seriously can considerably strengthen the
284 core of the empirical project in animal archaeologies, disclosing new research avenues and
285 possibilities for critical reflection and theorization, thereby alleviating the burden of received
286 presuppositions and propelling such archaeologies far beyond what has been termed “social
287 zooarchaeology” (Russell, 2012; Marciniak, 2020; Chazin, 2025). A zoo-ontological lens, I
288 hope to show, promotes evidential proximity and reinvigorates observation itself –
289 strengthening the voice of the archaeological record – while bringing into view multispecies
290 worlds that differ greatly from our own, challenging the many presentisms and anachronisms
291 plaguing the archaeology of human-animal relations for a long time. This onto-archaeology, I
292 argue, draws critical attention to the concreteness of lived human-animal relationships instead
293 of obsessing with how we abstract them – an animal archaeology that seeks to unearth non-
294 analogue and potentially excessively alien modes and logics of human-animal engagement
295 without continuously falling back into, and thereby naturalizing, the ontological registers of
296 what the late Sahlins (2022) termed post-axial “cultures of transcendence.”

297

⁶ I am not the first one to call onto this term in archaeology, of course, but even in Boyd’s (2017) recent call to for a post-anthropocentric human-animal archaeology the notion plays only a minor role and remains relatively unelaborated. This stands in notable contrast to the attention the idea of “zoontology” has gained in cultural studies (see esp. Wolfe, 2003 and contributions therein).

299 In a paper ahead of its time, Conneller (2004) suggested that prehistoric bodies are not what
300 they appear to be in the gaze of Linnaeus, Darwin, and Haeckel. Despite referencing the term
301 “ontological” only once, she argues that the treatment of human and animal bodies at early
302 Mesolithic Star Carr contradicts modern ideas of bodily boundedness, impartiality, and
303 immutability, elucidating the “way in which the human body is conceived” and the “types of
304 body produced from the taking on of objects made from animal remains” (Conneller, 2004: 37).
305 Drawing on the rich evidence from Star Carr, Conneller (2004) gestures towards corporeal
306 otherness not just in terms of how past people “perceived” bodies, but in terms of how they
307 enacted themselves as corporeal beings and engaged with other embodied entities, in turn also
308 shaping their situated yet nonetheless entangled ways of being and becoming (see also
309 Conneller, 2011). *Becoming deer* swirls up received ontological certainties of what a body is,
310 what bodies enable and effectuate, how they interrelate, and why particular bodies matter, and
311 others perhaps not so much (Conneller, 2004). How human and nonhuman bodies are treated,
312 brought into dialogue, manipulated, transformed, repositioned, staged, framed, and addressed,
313 in other words, can be highly informative of multispecies world-making (or “worlding”), i.e.,
314 the material-semiotic co-shaping of the shared context of human and nonhuman life in specific
315 times and places (Westerlaken, 2020; cf. Fredengren, 2021, 2022). Importantly, Conneller’s
316 (2004) exploration of red deer antler frontlets in the British early Mesolithic also un.masks
317 established scientific worldings and thereby reveals how implicit research ontologies more
318 often than not hamstring archaeological evidence: since Clark (1954: 170), the deer frontlets
319 are discussed as “headgear”, either understood as functional “hunting aids” or “ritual” remedies.
320 Conneller (2004: 37) notes that Clark “appeared to have covered all possibilities” and rightly
321 highlights that the thrust of the problem resides in its categorical “intransigence”. Yet, as she
322 lucidly exposes herself, this interpretive “impasse” is foremostly rooted in the conceptual
323 framing brought to bear on the antler frontlets, notably the idea that as “masks”, they are meant
324 to “disguise” rather than, for example, “reveal” (Conneller, 2004: 42).

325 The Star Carr antler frontlets are a perfect example of how our own commitments to
326 how the world supposedly is (and how it can thus be worked upon, not to speak of the idea that
327 world manipulation and control are “natural” aspirations) can interfere with the possibilities
328 afforded by the archaeological record. There are in reality much more than Clark’s two
329 possibilities, and this is not just a problem of so-called “unconceived alternatives” (Stanford,
330 2006), but how we have metaphysically positioned and partitioned ontology and epistemology,
331 so that the former appears to be necessarily singular and shared, while the latter is divisive
332 (embedded in and non-shared among different human cultures past and present). Material
333 culture either “responds to” and thus harnesses the supposedly shared ontological structure of
334 the world (functional explanation), it reveals particular “world-views” or “ways of seeing” this
335 world (symbolic/cosmological explanation: see esp. Barkai, 2021 for this use of ontology), or
336 a combination of the two. Expanding on Viveiros de Castro’s (1998; 2016) critique on the logic
337 of Western nature-culture binaries, ontology-epistemology relations may similarly be inverted,
338 could be otherwise, and they remain logically linked to Cartesian nature-culture construals. The
339 long-standing critique of “economic” approaches to human-animal relations at the heart of
340 recent developments in multispecies archaeology speaks to similar issues (e.g., Hamilakis and
341 Overton, 2013; Hill, 2013; Overton, 2016; Boyd, 2017): these approaches prioritize and thereby
342 tend to normalize particular ontological registers and the assumptions that come with the study
343 of particular places, times, peoples or lifestyles. The “economic” view, for example, is
344 frequently tied to capitalist notions of economy as “second nature” (see e.g., Cassegård, 2021)
345 and ideas of an “economy of nature” (Hussain, in press), with complicated but consequential
346 imports for the relationship between “nature”, “culture”, “ontology” and “epistemology” –
347 concepts we tend to group in neat pairings: ontology:nature vs. epistemology:culture. The

348 circumstance that animals are often grouped within the ontology:nature cluster is symptomatic
349 and important as such placement encourages the idea that they above all represent “resources”
350 for human societies to thrive (see Overton, 2016; Hill, 2021; Hussain and Brusgaard, 2024;
351 Mannermaa, 2025 for similar critiques). As such, animals are “effective” and “useful” because
352 of what they *invariantly are* (ontologically): bundles of energy, calories, and specific raw
353 materials (e.g., bone, horn, skin and sinew). Yet positioning animals as abstracted quantities
354 rather than in terms of their life-qualities and as embodied material and agentic beings merely
355 reveals the dominant (implicit) zoo-ontology of archaeological research. To simply invest into
356 *adding* “social” and “cultural” dimensions to the past significance of animals as proposed by
357 advocates of social zooarchaeology (Russell, 2012; Marciniak, 2020) and ethnozooarchaeology
358 (Albarella and Trentacoste, 2011; Broderick, 2016) tends to reinforce this general problem,
359 rather than to offer promising ways out of a serious ontological impasse. This is because,
360 importantly, none of the involved concepts (economy, resource, social, culture, etc.) is neutral,
361 and all of them pre-cast the material record in particular ways, opening specific possibilities of
362 insight, while closing off others. The way “economic” questions are conceptualized and posed
363 in much of traditional zooarchaeology, and in particular in its deep-time branches, provides a
364 telling example. Already in their influential *Manifesto for a Social Zooarchaeology*, Hamilakis
365 and Overton (2013: 177) note that much archaeological discussion on the target “economy” is
366 not at all about what they would like to interrogate under this rubric:

367 “[M]uch of the discussion to date has been in fact not on the economy – that is, on
368 relationships of entitlement, access and inequality – but on economizing – that is, on
369 formalist and rather mechanist allocation and management of narrowly defined
370 ‘resources’, an approach which obscures the socially embedded and corporeally
371 embodied nature of the economy. [...] [E]ven in contexts where humans have treated
372 animals as ‘resources’ to be exploited, such a relationship cannot be disentangled from
373 the effect of the bodily, sensuous, and often emotive encounters between humans and
374 other species, and the agentic power of each species to shape the other species’ life and
375 world: as living bodies, and as body substances and parts which are incorporated through
376 eating; hoarded, valued and preserved as mnemonic remnants; or transformed into
377 circulating, powerful objects, be they bone tools, trophies or animal masks.”

378 I suggest this is in large part because the history of zooarchaeology, especially what is today
379 considered “normal science” in the field (*sensu* Kuhn, [1962] 2020), was shaped by powerful
380 processualist ideas and concerns, often set off from the perspective of a general theory of human
381 behaviour (e.g., O’Connell, 1995; Rowley-Conwy, Serjeantson and Halstead, 2017), and
382 traditionally placing much emphasis on developing its broader knowledge-making apparatus
383 (e.g., Gifford-Gonzalez, 2018), yet exhibiting little awareness or recognition that its regulative
384 ideas (including those underpinning method-development) in fact relied on particular
385 ontological commitments and claims about humans, animals, the worlds they inhabited, and the
386 phenomena they participated in – many of which are now seen critically. Zooarchaeology is
387 thus an illuminating example of the structural role science can play in fortifying particular
388 zootologies, while marginalizing or even excluding others. Drawing on Wolfe’s (2003)
389 textbook dissection of modernist zootologies, archaeological apprehensions of “economy”,
390 “technology”, “sociality”, and “culture” can be said to rest on an ontological matrix in which
391 “humans” and “animals” are always separate and axiomatic and in which they therefore already
392 excludes each other, greatly limiting what we can notice and know about their gatherings, let
393 alone about multispecies worlds premised on other types of categorical order.

394 Even so, and notwithstanding the obvious weight of ontology on recent developments
395 in multispecies archaeology (Hill, 2011; Boyd, 2017; Harris and Cipolla, 2017b; Oma
396 Armstrong, 2018; Armstrong-Oma, 2021; Živaljević, 2021), the concern with ontology remains

397 generic and archaeologists rarely speak of or explicitly engage “zoo-ontology” (Boyd, 2017:
398 307-309; Hill, 2021). This situation has likely to do with two overarching preoccupations of
399 much current ontology-informed animal archaeology: 1) the “ontological lens” is deployed
400 primarily as a critical manoeuvre to expose Western Cartesian research frameworks and their
401 conceptual and interpretive limitations for the study of past multispecies relationships (e.g.,
402 Armstrong Oma, 2018; Chazin, 2024; Mannermaa, 2025); and 2) “ontology” is still widely
403 regarded and used above all as a basic matrix to organize and supply input categories of
404 observation and interpretation rather than as an empirical variable itself (e.g., Kveiborg,
405 Ahlqvist and Vandkilde, 2020; McNiven, 2022; Mansrud, 2023). The former has led to all sorts
406 of calls for making away with Western dichotomous thinking altogether, which is likely
407 delusional at best, and has incentivized many to emphatically turn to Indigenous perspectives
408 and ontologies in order to source alternative means to interrogate the archaeological past (e.g.,
409 Herva, 2009; Laguens, 2024). This “Indigenization” of the past is not only productive, however,
410 as Indigenous perspectives are often reified in the process, past difference is easily
411 homogenized, and some forms of past otherness equally denied – the “we have always been
412 like this” syndrome of primordialism. Invoking Indigenous ontologies bears similar problems
413 as invoking ethnographic analogies (Alberti, 2016 speaks of the “authorized return of the grand
414 ethnographic analogy in archaeology”): specific ontologies need to be selected from a wide
415 pool of existing and possible ontologies, and scholars are in most cases also forced to work with
416 specific *representations* of these ontologies, which may be contested, variously interest-laden,
417 and/or distorted themselves. Viveiros de Castro’s (1998) account of Amerindian perspectivism
418 is a prime example of this challenge as the author does not dismiss the nature-culture polarity
419 but rather argues that “nature” and “culture” are differentially linked to each other and other
420 key concepts, thus unveiling a world-making logic substantially deviating from default Western
421 reality-making. His account (1998; 2016), furthermore, comes as a specific interpretation of the
422 set of ethnographic observations referred to – it is a specific “worlding” of this evidence itself.
423 In this broader rendering of the problem of ontology, Ribeiro’s (2019) critique does thus not
424 fail its mark. Brokering of ontologies as such – as ready-made devices of research – and to
425 assess their *a priori* appropriateness threatens to simply shift the debate on inferior/superior
426 (research) perspectives from the epistemological to the ontological level.

427 Archaeologists can therefore not simply substitute what they would have previously
428 considered their scientific epistemology with a specific ontological lens, just because this lens
429 (e.g., perspectivism, animism) is currently *en vogue*, because it is also routinely deployed by
430 other archaeologists (paragon bias), or because the deep past is imaged as “animist” (period
431 bias, easily reinforced by e.g., influential shamanist stereotypes: cf. Clottes, Lewis-Williams
432 and Clottes, 1998). The “epistemologization” of ontology, in other words, cannot solve the
433 problems the ontological critique set out to address, to the contrary: in many cases, new
434 problems of the same kind will be reintroduced. Yet the talk about “flat ontologies” (Harris and
435 Cipolla, 2017b), “relational ontologies” (Herva, 2009), “sociocentric ontologies” (Mansrud,
436 2023) or “kin-centric ontologies” (McNiven, 2022), and about “animism” or “perspectivism”
437 as specific research frameworks or as distinct approaches (Mansrud and Berg-Hansen, 2021;
438 Mansrud, 2023) is symptomatic of these understandings, in practice often reinforcing other
439 ontology-epistemology hierarchies rather than opening them up. We may argue that as long as
440 these perspectives are cultivated in the plural, contrasted, and critiqued, and as long as they
441 develop no hegemonic claims on archaeological pasts, they can help illuminate previously
442 overlooked aspects or uncover otherwise disclosed otherness and difference. And this is
443 certainly a reasonable position to take, but we must also be vigilant that we do not on the way
444 confuse the “ontologies” we mobilize to enact our scholarship with those we seek to *reveal*
445 through sustained archaeological investigation and concept-work. This confusion, I suggest, is
446 often at play when archaeologists engaging with such issues become “metaphysical

447 archaeologists” in the way Alberti (2016) describes them, wittingly or not introducing
448 “alternative metaphysical orthodoxy” to the discipline. All of this is somewhat ironic as
449 ontological archaeologies were originally devised to combat all forms of orthodoxy – precisely
450 to make space for alterity and difference. The critique on “interpretation” ushered in by early
451 proponents of ontological archaeologies was for instance squarely targeted at the conventional
452 idea that meaning and significance are exclusively human provinces and epitomize *arbitrary*
453 affairs (Alberti, Jones and Pollard, 2013). Acceptance of the plurality of interpretation was
454 hence typically premised on, and so purchased at the expense of, the singularity of ontology.
455 The critique on interpretive archaeologies now needs to be reformulated as pointing to the
456 *inseparability* of description and interpretation in the wake of co-pluralities – the plurality of
457 epistemology-ontology arrangements and relations, as well as the plurality of “concepts of
458 concepts” (Brandom, 2001). All of this harkens back on the insistence of critical scholars such
459 as Latour (2018) that no description can hope to be neutral or un-political – every description
460 is ontologically infused – and we must thus actively practice and cultivate our capacity to
461 describe from a standpoint of difference (Muecke, 2024; Muecke *et al.*, 2025).

462 Interpretation is therefore not simply for the garbage bin. It must be re-activated in the
463 service of the ontological critique, as part of the antidote to the continuous closure of onto-
464 epistemological registers of knowing the past. But this also means that the traditional role of
465 interpretation is changed: interpretation is no longer about reaching out to the arbitrary (which
466 may reasonably be dubbed “speculation”) but fundamentally concerned with the *nexus of doing,*
467 *knowing, and being:* how worlds take shape through the tangled practices of particular agents,
468 in turn enacting specific realities affording specific ways of seeing, knowing, and engaging.
469 Material and visual traces register the organization and logic of these worlds but also take part
470 in their enactment, curation, and reproduction. Bodies, artefacts, and images are “worlded”, i.e.,
471 shaped by their worlds, but they coevally shape and thereby assemble these worlds (Eitler,
472 2014). We can then productively ask what the specific ecologies of observed visual and material
473 traces are, and what kinds of ontological registers they premise, actualize, and afford. This is
474 by and large an empirical question, but one that cannot be addressed without *ontological*
475 *literacy.* This literacy is not reducible to the taking on of particular ontological positionalities,
476 it indeed clashes with such an inclination and instead demands sensibility for the kinds of
477 ontological difference we may encounter in varying contexts, and so requires familiarity with
478 broader ontological debates, positions, conflicts, and the anthropology of difference. There is
479 no easy way out of this and no reduction to singularity; taking ontology seriously is extremely
480 difficult and challenging – it is antithetical to the rhetorics of simplicity.

481 With this understanding of the archaeological record as both a product and context of
482 negotiating specific ways of doing, knowing, and being, in which material objects and visual
483 renditions play an active and conducive role, we can now productively turn to some
484 opportunities of engaging with the ontology of past animals and human-animal relations – what
485 I collectively refer to as “zoo-ontology” here (*sensu* Wolfe, 2003), even though zoontology is
486 always available in the plural, and, even worse, much of this plurality space is unknown for the
487 past and deep past as currently used ontological categories were elaborated from contemporary
488 or at least ethnohistorical source materials (see esp. Descola, 2005, 2021). With this in mind, it
489 seems indispensable to return to the archaeological record and its capacity to resist and escape
490 our own ontological registers (Hussain, 2025b). As a starting point, I will explore the
491 ontological bearings of archaeological patterns of non-arbitrarily referring to or incorporating
492 other animal materialities with a particular eye for discussions in Palaeolithic and Mesolithic
493 archaeology, and then do the same with regard to what has been termed Palaeolithic visual
494 culture (Nowell, 2017). My goal is to sketch a larger research endeavour fuelled by the
495 ontological critique capable of advancing the aims of deep-time animal archaeologies and to
496 show that a more courageous, literal reading of observable human-animal entanglements can

497 help break long-standing ontological impositions, brining into view previously clouded logics
498 of human-animal engagement and their associated material patterns.

499

500 *From materialities to zoomaterialities: the nexus of animal bodies*

501 The materiality of nonhuman animals is a pervasive component and integral feature of the
502 archaeological record (Hussain, 2024a). We can collectively refer to this corpus of animal
503 material traces as “zoomateriality” – material culture made from animal bodies, body-parts, and
504 other animal-derived products. Archaeological zoomaterialities are extremely diverse and
505 exhibit both small-scale and large-scale spatiotemporal patterning evading simple logics of
506 availability, suitability, and Cartesian usefulness (“utility” tied to specific notions of causality
507 and mechanical action as derived from the so-called “effective” categories of mechanistic
508 thought: cf. Pepper, 1972: Chapter IX). And yet, there is widespread belief in the field that
509 organic tools sourced and made from animal bodies somehow respond to the raw material
510 requirements of such tool-making (e.g., Knecht, 1997a; Choyke and O’Connor, 2013; Hutson
511 *et al.*, 2018). Body parts were selected, in other words, because of their conformity with key
512 (and likely aspired) tooling parameters such as workability, shape, size, durability, sturdiness,
513 and compactness (e.g., Iovita and Sano, 2016; Langley, 2016; Wild *et al.*, 2022). Even though
514 experimental research confirms a nonarbitrary linkage between some of these material
515 dimensions of faunal remains and their human treatment in the archaeological record (e.g.,
516 Pfeifer *et al.*, 2019 for ivory properties), the extent to which the hypothesized key parameters
517 can predict the details of observed tool-related engagements with animal bodies remains to be
518 explored and is likely to hold considerable surprises to researchers.

519 Part of the problem is how animal-sourced tooling is commonly conceptualized: people
520 are typically said to either select their organic raw materials (bone, antler, horn, or ivory)
521 because of their formal and abstracted, material qualities believed to be required for certain
522 tools to work properly and effectively (e.g., Pétillon, 2008; Pfeifer *et al.*, 2019; Backwell and
523 d’Errico, 2020), or they select whatever animal remains are “opportune” to be used in relevant
524 ways, often with minimal technical interference as opportunistic use is regularly understood as
525 dependent on the existence of functional working ends such as tips or fresh sharp edges already
526 inherent in the original configuration of animal body elements (e.g., Tartar, 2012; Hutson *et al.*,
527 2018; Ma and Doyon, 2021; Abrams *et al.*, 2025). In the first scenario, the idea of the tool and
528 its requirements logically proceed the selection process, reproducing the notion of animal
529 bodies as a bundle of distinct “resources” whose value can be reduced to their physical and
530 geochemical properties and detached from the living animal of which they were once a part;
531 tool-making here is cast simply as a siloed, function-securing exercise of exclusive human
532 province, while “function” is largely understood as mechanistic action with source-independent
533 but predictable consequences. The functionality of these animal-sourced tools can consequently
534 be “curated” and “honed” (Knecht, 1997b) and the analytical focus thus regularly lies on the
535 various human modification and shaping practices needed to translate this material potential
536 into specific human-sought functions (e.g., de la Torre *et al.*, 2025). The second scenario
537 situates determination on the other extreme of the spectrum and humans are cast as hyper-
538 adaptive opportunity seekers discovering and co-opting predefined faunal functionalities; yet,
539 again, these functionalities are primarily understood in physicalist and mechanistic terms, as
540 “performance characteristics” in the sense of Schiffer and Skibo (1997; Skibo and Schiffer,
541 2008). This opportunity-seeking mode of organic raw material selection and transformation is
542 often accompanied with a description of what has been called “expedient” design (Lyman,
543 1984; Doyon *et al.*, 2021). Both perspectives rest on particular notions of how animal-oriented
544 tool-making works, what it is about, why it matters, and what role animal bodies themselves
545 play in the process. They are not only anthropocentric and thus delegate almost no significance

546 to the involved animals beyond rendering them as the inert husks of their abstracted morpho-
547 physical properties accidentally tied to their durable body parts, they also, at best, outline only
548 a rather narrow subset of possibilities with regard to the logics of selection, the role of animal
549 bodies, and the nature of tool-making, to name but a few sites of contention. Part of the
550 ontological register that feeds this conceptualization, in other words, appears to be the
551 assumption that faunal selection for tool production is chiefly *output-oriented*, the output is
552 independent from the embodied context of its input, and cognition is upstream, i.e., takes
553 precedence over, and ultimately determines, material engagement, rather than being *embedded*
554 in the latter. All of these propositions are problematic (e.g., Malafouris, 2015; Hussain, 2018;
555 Ihde and Malafouris, 2019; Hussain and Will, 2021), and they reverberate particular
556 zoontologies of the present, not even necessarily shared among the diverse academic and
557 intellectual traditions cultivated in the West (see esp. Pepper, 1972).

558 Reformulating the problem in the following way may help to illustrate what is at stake
559 here: although it seems uncontroversial that past humans appear to have “used” animal bodies
560 in particular ways as we can clearly observe in, and attest through, the archaeological record,
561 *what* precisely humans have used (e.g., have they used detached Cartesian bones or did they
562 instead use relational “bear-feet”?) and *why* they have used it (e.g., did they use them primarily
563 or exclusively to exert physical action or rather attempted to enact “bear-feet-ness”?) should be
564 opened up for interrogation rather than prescribed by the dominant zoontologies of research. It
565 is precisely there, I would argue, that valuable insights into pasts otherwise can be gleaned,
566 telling us something new about the situated interposition of tools, animals, and people in past
567 contexts and their ontological bearings. Such situated ontological registers are expected to
568 impinge on human cognition, categorization, meaning-making, and notably the *how* of animal
569 body treatment and zoomaterial transformation, which also includes different technological
570 modes of attending to faunal remains. As these various dimensions of past realities are expected
571 to co-configure each other, evidence-driven analysis worthy of this designation must strive to
572 free itself from as many *a priori* conceptual fixings as possible. This is the reason why
573 ontological investigations in archaeology are fundamentally troubled by deductive reasoning,
574 especially when such reasoning is based on so-called (near)certainties of how the world truly is
575 (typically derived from authoritative universal theories of reality).⁷ It is also important to
576 remember, however, that such opening up of the archaeological possibility space does not mean
577 to *a priori* discount the all of the respectively “unfixed” and criticized categories and concepts
578 either; it may in fact be demonstrated that some of these categories have great relevance for
579 archaeological explanation and contextual understanding (see e.g., Russell, 2022), but this
580 remains an empirical task and must thus be discerned on a case-to-case basis.

581 Returning to the question of what is “used” in zoomaterialities and why other bodies are
582 engaged and to what effect, scholars are therefore well-advised to critically scrutinize the twin
583 notion that 1) animal-sourced tools are primarily instruments to act on the world, and that 2)
584 the “effect” of such tools in the world resides primarily in their ability to elicit physical-material
585 action as a consequence of the properties of the inert matter contained in the animals in question.
586 In response to 1), we may insist that zoomateriality frequently serves as a potent means to *enact*
587 the world and to negotiate, mediate, and forge particular social and interspecies relationships,
588 and not others (e.g. Hill, 2013, 2021; Eitler, 2014; Hussain, Weiss and Kellberg Nielsen, 2022);
589 in response to 2), we may point to the distinctiveness of Western construals of causality and
590 mechanistic action, notably the circumstance that material “efficacy” in cross-cultural
591 perspective often makes reference to nonmaterial aspects of the very materiality considered, for
592 example the qualities and behaviours associated with the living animals in question (see esp.
593 Hamilakis, 2003; Borić, 2005; Jones, 2009; Conneller, 2011; Živaljević, 2015; Hill, 2019;

⁷ However, I do not believe that a new “inductionism” follows from this as Furholt (2023) seems to suggest.

594 Hussain, 2023, in pressa), including the recognition of the potential WEIRD-ness⁸ of the very
595 idea that death renders matter inert and ends animal agency.

596 Taking these considerations seriously helps to reconfigure our knowledge space of
597 archaeological pasts and can disclose alternative perspectives on the relationship between
598 zoomateriality and past human-animal relations. As often in such cases, it is instructive to begin
599 with a critical analysis of our Western, highly entrenched scientific gaze. In an important study
600 hardly known or cited in archaeology, Cory Willmott (2014) has for example shown that
601 animals and people can intersect in dramatically different ways vis-à-vis practices of identity
602 construction and maintenance, and that these are contingent on divergent ways of being in the
603 world, or what she calls their “modes of production”. She argues that Great Lakes Algonquians
604 and their European colonizers showcase contrasting modes of identity negotiation rooted not in
605 differences of symbolic attendance but with regard to the *ontological pertinence of the visual*.
606 In the Algonquian case, the “realm of the visual” plays a far lesser role than in the European
607 case and animal behaviours and lived corporealities are overriding vectors of identity politics –
608 the specificities of the “behavioural environment” enacted by embodied animals – to some
609 extent recapitulating the tension between Linnean taxonomy foregrounding animal appearance
610 (shape, morphology) and Indigenous ordering systems emphasizing difference through
611 (situationally) enacted effects (see e.g., Zedeño, 2009, 2013; cf. Hussain, in pressc). These
612 contrasting logics of identity construction are associated with disparate relationships and
613 attitudes towards beavers and sheep respectively – they critically feed into these relationships
614 and are fed by them, both performatively and cognitively (Willmott, 2014).

615 Alongside the heavy weight often put on appearance-based as well as formal, casually-
616 effective characteristics of animal bodies to act upon the world, we should equally question the
617 assumption of invariant separateness, boundedness, and impartiality of human and animal
618 bodies. As Hill (2021: 27) notes, selective depositions of paradigmatic animal body parts such
619 as skulls, for example of beluga whales in Southwest Alaska, “middening” of such body parts,
620 inclusion of more-or-less complete animals or specific body elements into human burials, and
621 the deliberate caching of similar objects, for example deer antler, “suggest that animal agency
622 and personhood were key components of many zoontologies.” Integrating archaeological and
623 anthropological data, McNiven (2010, 2022) has argued that in later Holocene Torres Strait
624 Northeast Australia Indigenous peoples’ relationship with animal bodies was not foremostly
625 instrumental or overtly “economic” but instead *dialogical*, again reflected in zoomaterialities
626 incorporating body parts of key animal others, for example dugong ear bones. This human
627 choice is poorly understood as an arbitrary symbolic act of signification, however, and I argue
628 that we should probe into the possibilities of appreciating such zooselectivity much more
629 literally and with regard to concrete human-animal expositions in shared multispecies
630 lifeworlds: dugongs are marine keystone agents maintaining the coastal seagrass meadows, they
631 ensure the productivity of the land-sea interface, they anchor particular seagrass species
632 communities (many of which past humans relied on) (cf. e.g., Bakker *et al.*, 2016), and they do
633 so by deploying their heads; the special treatment of ear bones may then be interpreted as
634 *conducting* this deep existential enmeshment of dugongs and Indigenous people and to
635 contribute to the resulting necessity of dialogical interspecies engagement, perhaps even
636 human-dugong diplomacy: ear bones enable cross-species communication due to their original
637 bodily “function” in these living coastal megaherbivores. Ear bones may hence link a
638 particularly salient human-animal relationship with the efficaciousness of the animal bodily
639 functions contained in this relationship by virtue of the key role of ears and heads in dugong

⁸ In cross-cultural psychology, WEIRD stands for “Western, Educated, Industrialized, Rich and Democratic”, the dominant population sample underpinning most generalized statements on human cognition and behaviour in psychology and other behavioural sciences (Henrich, 2020).

640 human-directed world-making. In this view, animal raw material selection has less to do with
641 the harnessing of Cartesian functionalities: “functionalities” may instead be a consequence of
642 the world-making agencies and bodily capabilities of particular animal others, and these vary
643 in efficacy, co-optational potential, and have a corporeal *location* of their own. Triangulating
644 zoomaterialities with animal ecosystem and world-making agencies as well as human
645 needscales, lifeworld concerns, and cohabitational arrangements may therefore pry open novel
646 windows into the ontological fabric of past multispecies worlds.

647 Extending and refining Borić’s (2005) exploration of “bodily volatility”, Živaljević
648 (2015) has similarly argued that concepts of the body and personhood were brokered in the
649 Mesolithic-Neolithic of the Danube Gorges – comprising Lepenski Vir and other sites – by
650 drawing on specific body parts, manipulating them and re-arranging them in different contexts,
651 in house floors or burial contexts. Importantly, body-part selectivity is highly patterned and not
652 arbitrary: it appears to be grounded in embodied and affective animals, “how they look, feel or
653 what they *do*” (Živaljević, 2015: 675, original emphasis). Difference here is produced and
654 created not through the abstract extraction of the animals’ ahistorical “essences”, but with
655 reference to how animals help to enact a shared world and how they differ in this regard and
656 their human exposition from other animals. Živaljević (2015) suggests that deer antlers were
657 often deposited in house contexts and floors because of their “regenerative” properties, notably
658 contrasting the treatment of bovid horns, and that dog mandibles as the locus of “dog speech”
659 (barking, etc.) were drawn upon to co-opt the distinct “communicative” capabilities and vantage
660 points of dogs. Importantly, bringing together animal body parts in novel configurations, in
661 association with human remains or not, is argued to proffer a potent means to create *new kinds*
662 *of bodies* (Živaljević, 2015: 684-685), neither necessarily “human” nor “animal”. This
663 possibility illustrates the ability of zoontological analysis to disrupt humanist ordering practices
664 (Wolfe, 2003) and transferring Krupnik and colleagues’ (2012) evocation of the more-than-
665 human “nonempirical past” into the theatre of death (not only challenging Western
666 understandings of death but also of what can be said to exist and under what conditions). How
667 bodies travel through space and especially time, participate in other bodies, transform, and give
668 way to new bodies must be considered a key arena of human engagement and intervention and
669 attests to varied and perhaps multiple transient ontologies of the body negotiated in relation to
670 human and nonhuman rhythms and defusing the idea that death implies the cessation of bodily
671 potency and agency, rather than marking yet another transition in bodily potentiality and
672 affectivity. That animal bodies are partible and capable to enact and reproduce significant social
673 relationships is also reflected in the treatment of dog bodies, notably the removal of the head,
674 mirroring similar practices in human burials, but not other animals (Živaljević, 2015: 692). A
675 similar relationship between people and foxes has been proposed at the Eipipalaeolithic site of
676 Uyun al-Hammam in Jordan on the eastern side of the Mediterranean Sea, where a fairly
677 complete fox body was partitioned between two human burial contexts by means of
678 translocating the skull (Maher *et al.*, 2011); this case is interesting because only humans and
679 foxes but no other animals appear to have received such treatment, pointing to zoontological
680 registers operating oblique to, or even beyond, the human-animal divide.

681 Body part selectivity – sometimes more subtle, other times more pronounced – has also
682 been documented for the European Middle Palaeolithic, even though many patterns are still
683 unclear and await clarification (see e.g., Wragg Sykes, 2020; Hussain, Weiss and Kellberg
684 Nielsen, 2022; Hussain, 2023). Some Neanderthals placed special emphasis on bear feet bones
685 and paws, the former were often co-opted for stone-tool retouchers (Abrams *et al.*, 2014), or
686 extracted bear pelts without necessarily exploiting full bear bodies (Verheijen *et al.*, 2023),
687 some used elephant ribs to turn them into “spears” and “lances” (Gaudzinski *et al.*, 2005),
688 fur/skin smoothers were often made from aurochs and bison ribs (Soressi *et al.*, 2013), and deer
689 femora were frequently deployed as retouchers (Romero *et al.*, 2023), as were horse incisors

690 (Baumann *et al.*, 2023), even though the articulation of these zoo-objects with other organic
691 and inorganic tool-making practices remains elusive (see Hussain, in pressa for an overview of
692 the data). These patterns not only illustrate the limitations of the function-symbol framework,
693 they point to the pivotal role of embodied animals and their varied agencies in structuring
694 Middle Palaeolithic zoomaterialities. In a notable number of cases, for example, patterns of
695 selectivity appear to be disjunct from overarching foci of Neanderthal subsistence: at Chez-
696 Pinaud in France, a diverse Neanderthal bone-tool assemblage is mainly sourced from larger
697 ungulates and especially osseous “multi-tools” appear to have been almost exclusively
698 manufactured from their bones, yet smaller reindeer dominate the rich faunal assemblage
699 associated with the site (Baumann *et al.*, 2022). In the broader techno-economic context referred
700 to as “Quina” (or “Quina Mousterian”, due to the reliance on Quina technology linked to a
701 distinct mobility system: cf. Delagnes and Rendu, 2011), Neanderthals preferentially engaged
702 in systematic, often large-scale reindeer hunting, yet reindeer bones are treated highly
703 selectively: they were rarely modified, often mainly used as fuel, and when transformed used
704 as blanks for end-smoothed and bevelled tools (Baumann *et al.*, 2023) – a choice hardly
705 intelligible simply as “opportunistic”. Instead, these patterns likely reveal varying positions,
706 potentialities, and potencies both of animal bodies and specific body parts within Neanderthal
707 ontologies, including their status as “bodies”, “persons”, materialized “capacities”, etc., to
708 begin with. As Hamilakis (2008, 2013) has persuasively argued before, even the consumption
709 of other bodies is never a neutral exercise and hence a “key arena of interspecies engagement”
710 (Hamilakis and Overton, 2013: 117), as bodies are literally incorporated, integrated, and
711 changed when eaten, devoured, or feasted upon. The taking on of animal bodies, behaviours,
712 sensibilities and qualities is thus not limited to the treatment of their organic body parts but can
713 be relevant to our understanding of other body-related practices, too. “Clothing” is another such
714 practice as people literally cloak themselves in certain animals and so “extend” or otherwise
715 alter their own bodies (see e.g. Živaljević, 2015: 678), both materially and virtually. It is
716 therefore possible that the restrictive utilization of reindeer for organic tool-making in Quina
717 contexts is logically tied to the regular *incorporation of their bodies through consumption*, so
718 that acquisition of reindeer “functionalities” required no separate efforts.

719 These examples highlight that patterns of selection and treatment underpinning different
720 archaeological zoomaterialities regularly challenge the very ontological registers researchers
721 are used to draw upon to make sense of the past. They also showcase the importance of starting
722 to engage the possibility of multispecies worlds otherwise, and that practices, knowledges, and
723 ontologies were co-configured and articulated in different and sometimes surprising ways
724 through them. The alleged “use” of animals as “raw material” offers a productive starting point
725 for such critical interrogations in human-animal archaeologies as notions of “usefulness” and
726 “functionality”, what can actually be harnessed from specific animals, for what purposes, and
727 what human practices *do* with specific animals and in shared human-animal worlds are
728 powerfully opened up for empirical analysis and reinterpretation. Archaeological patterns of
729 zoomaterial selection and animal body treatment often suggest that already usability and
730 functionality – traditional vectors of zooarchaeological research – cannot be understood outside
731 of a broader landscape of animal-oriented *affordances* (Gibson, 1977; Rietveld and Kiverstein,
732 2014) and *multispecies affordances* (van Dijk, 2021), as how to make best use of animal bodies,
733 in what ways and to what effects is not a question of abstract reflection but revealed through
734 concrete relationships tailored in the world and actions performed in it. The co-optation,
735 reclamation, and transposition of relevant potentials for action and thought as well as of
736 qualities and efficacies registered by particular animal body-parts is therefore a theme that
737 merits extended comparative and systematic investigation. Archaeological evidence mustered
738 in support of such practices bring into view the porosity, mutability, and fluidity of bodies and
739 the portability of faculties, perspectives, and potentials (Hill, 2019), thus enabling the

740 archaeological study of engaged animal body differences through time and space. As Hussain
741 and Brusgaard (2024) have pointed out, the human-animal *recursivity* of some of these practices
742 is noteworthy: beaver mandibles in the Mesolithic of Northern Europe were co-opted almost as
743 they are in order to (re-)enact similar beaver “effects” in the environment; as a practice, this
744 essentially translates beaver agency into human domains and fosters a “beaver perspective” on
745 how to navigate and operate in the respective environments. Examples like this may be much
746 more common than currently admitted but a final example must suffice here: the cooccurrence
747 of minimally modified tiger shark teeth from Middle Holocene Sulawesi Toalean hunter-
748 gatherer contexts with so-called lithic “Maros points” exhibiting over-serendipitous shape
749 similarity with the same shark teeth (Langley *et al.*, 2023). Not only does this association
750 similarly suggest a sort of “borrowing” or “translation” of specific shark agencies, efficacies,
751 and “functionalities”, it again shows how difficult it is to overcome rehearsed research logics:
752 the brittleness of the teeth preventing recurrent use and effective resharpening were initially
753 taken to indicate a broadly “ritual” significance of the items by the authors. But should we not
754 ask instead: what if the functionality of the shark teeth had less to do with their physical
755 properties? What if the teeth were part of a process of learning, co-opting, and appropriating
756 shark “functionalities” whose refined incorporation into human culture is reflected in Maros
757 points as such a translation of “shark dentition” does not suffer from brittleness?

758

759 *From visualities to zoovisualities: the nexus of animal images*

760 Nonhuman animals participate in past visual worlds, both directly and indirectly (see Hussain,
761 in pressa for a recent synthesis). They are rendered and evoked, even though the specificity of
762 the animal is sometimes left ambiguous (Davidson, 2025), and their diverse agencies,
763 affectivities, and behavioural legacies play into the formation of the visual (Hussain, 2025c).
764 As recently elaborated by Wisher and colleagues (2023), many visual forms, especially in the
765 context of Upper Palaeolithic parietal art, must be understood as “conversational” practices; as
766 “installation art” (Sakamoto, 2019), these visualities are regularly staged by and stage their
767 material environment, and they are inextricably embedded in this environment (e.g., Robert,
768 2007, 2011; Lorblanchet, 2010; Pastoors and Weniger, 2011; Delannoy *et al.*, 2013; Batarda
769 Fernandes *et al.*, 2017; Lorblanchet and Bahn, 2017; David *et al.*, 2021; Hussain, 2025c). As a
770 result, the respective imaging practices often evade simple qualifications as “representational”
771 or “symbolic” – they yield diverse synthetic properties and bricolage qualities (see esp. Conkey
772 and Fisher, 2020; Hughes, 2021), frame hybrid “naturecultures” (Hussain, 2025c), and belabour
773 mineral-animal resemblances on local and landscape scales (e.g., Coulson, Staurset and Walker,
774 2011; Nash and Garcês, 2023), resulting in what with Marchesini (2018) may be termed
775 “zoomorphisms”. As in the context of zoomateriality discussed in the previous section, this
776 draws in the question of ontology, not just because the long-standing obsession with identifying
777 the correct “zoo-reference” (see Sauvet *et al.*, 2009; Sauvet, 2019 for some examples) may in
778 many cases entirely miss the point, but also because notions such as “art”, “religion”, and
779 “spiritual culture” may fundamentally abduct the purpose and logic of the corresponding
780 practices (see e.g., White, 1992; Conkey and Fisher, 2020; Moro Abadía and Porr, 2021; Abadía
781 and Tapper, 2025). This concern with our ability to know and understand visual pasts otherwise
782 has to be sharply distinguished, I suggest, from the emancipatory opportunities that arise from
783 the affirmation of “art” as a tractable deep-time phenomenon (see e.g., Porr, 2019). To combat
784 the many conceptual delusions that likely mislead our apprehension of “zoovisuality” (cf.
785 Hussain, in pressa) – visual culture (Nowell, 2017) as it pertains to animal imagery in and on

786 various media⁹ – we must accordingly not only ask what an animal image *is*,¹⁰ but also open up
787 our situated understandings of “realism” (BernÁldez-Sánchez and García-Viñas, 2019),
788 “depictional accuracy” (Horvath *et al.*, 2012), as well as *why* the (zoo)visual is conjured in the
789 first place (see esp. Jones, 2021). The burden of implicit assumptions as to the nature of such
790 “art” as “representational” weighs heavily on this enterprise (e.g., Davidson, 1999; Guthrie,
791 2005; Renfrew and Morley, 2009; Sauvet *et al.*, 2009; Clottes, 2011; Walker, Clinnick and
792 Pedersen, 2018; Solomon, 2019; Bacon *et al.*, 2023) and I will focus here on a range of reasons
793 why it may be productive to initially dispense with this influential idea when interrogating
794 Palaeolithic zoovisualities. Once more, we should more seriously consider that zoovisuality
795 may register the *literal* rather than the abstract and arbitrary of lived human-animal
796 intersections, participate in the construction and negotiation of situated interspecies relations,
797 and hence should not readily be exiled to the realm of mere “signs” or “visual communication”
798 (Davidson, 2025), especially since the latter immediately taps into related assumptions that the
799 subjects of communication (i.e., relevant interlocutors) are exclusive human.

800 To begin addressing some of these issues, it is useful to centre the attention on an old –
801 some would perhaps say outdated – problem, namely the relationship between archaeological
802 zoovisuality and living past animal ecologies (see e.g., Guthrie, 2005; Azéma and Rivère, 2012;
803 Korpershoek *et al.*, 2024). Framing this as an essential locus of insight simply *assumes* that
804 zoovisuality *is* representational, either by representing the “real”, that is the external
805 environment, or by representing the “imagined”, i.e., the internal environment (e.g., Hodgson,
806 2003, 2021). Importantly, Upper Palaeolithic cave art in particular is often precast as a
807 representational phenomenon *par excellence*, in large part because of the tendency to regard
808 “representational art” as the hallmark of *Homo sapiens* (e.g., Bourrillon and White, 2015), while
809 Neanderthals are argued to inhabit “non-representational” cognitive worlds (Coss, 2017); the
810 ontological challenge, however, is to render representationality yet another hypothesis to put to
811 the test in different spatiotemporal contexts, rather than to naturalize it as a species baseline (cf.
812 Jones, 2021).¹¹ Both the “real” and the “imagined” tend to presuppose an objectivist and realist
813 ontology (and cultural epistemologies harkening back on it), which we cannot take for granted,
814 but need to demonstrate by weight of the available archaeological evidence. Consider for
815 example the many paradoxes arising from allegedly “exotic”, “rare” or possibly “(near)extinct”
816 animals in Palaeolithic zoovisuality: archaeologists regularly argue (both in press and in
817 reviews) that the circumstance of depiction alone must be evidence for animal presence, the
818 details of such depictions, if elaborated, must suggest direct observation, and that megafaunal
819 depictions can therefore be mobilized as evidence for dating megafaunal survival (e.g., Bosinski
820 and Bosinski, 1991; Iriarte *et al.*, 2022; Korpershoek *et al.*, 2024; Richter *et al.*, 2024a). These
821 construals are not only based on the idea that depiction is a practice of indexing something else
822 “out there”, they also clearly fall prey to circular reasoning. More seriously, they confound the
823 richness of conveyed details with pictorial “realism” or “naturalism” (e.g., Pruvost *et al.*, 2011;
824 BernÁldez-Sánchez and García-Viñas, 2019)¹², quickly invoke “real-world observation” (see

⁹ The qualification “zoo” may in the future be reserved for more inclusively usage, to denote both human and nonhuman animals (from the Greek ζῷον *zōon*, “animal”), also to further destabilize the human-animal boundary. We may then further distinguish between “anthrovisualities” and “theriovisualities”, for example. The same of course applies to the qualification “zoomateriality” discussed in the previous section.

¹⁰ The ontology of Palaeolithic imagery is a still poorly explored theme, but often defies Western assumptions and intuitions on “art” and “imagery”, for example with regard to the boundedness and discreteness of an image. In an attempt to understand Upper Palaeolithic cave art, Davies (2025) has accordingly proposed an “ontological contextualism”, defining art not based on properties contained within its anthropogenic boundaries, but on its interrelationality with other environmental features as well as its embeddedness in such features.

¹¹ For the long and troubled history of thinking through Palaeolithic art from the vantage point of Western modernity and its obsession with realism and abstraction, see Stavrinaki (2022).

¹² Consider for this symptomatic line of reasoning from the abstract of Pruvost and colleagues (2011): “[...] all horse color phenotypes that seem to be distinguishable in cave paintings have now been found to exist in prehistoric

825 also Abadía, González Morales and Pérez, 2012), and posit that details are antithetical to
826 memory-based visual productions (Guthrie, 2005). This is easily linked to the assumption that
827 cultural memory in societies which rely on oral and communicative transmission is less accurate
828 and possesses a shorter half-life when compared to more recent literate societies; both
829 impositions are problematic in light of available evidence from Indigenous contexts (e.g.,
830 Ouzman *et al.*, 2002; Nunn, 2019; Hamacher *et al.*, 2023). The difficulty is not that these
831 contestations are always wrong, the problem is that we cannot confidently know whether they
832 are if we close them off from empirical scrutiny. It may well be, for example, that Palaeolithic
833 societies have memorized in particular selected (salient) details of relevant animals and codified
834 them in particular visual conventions such as distinctive ways of drawing back or ventral
835 contour-lines rather than attending to animals as bounded wholes (see e.g., Lorblanchet, 2010;
836 Lorblanchet and Bahn, 2017; Conkey and Fisher, 2020; Hodgson, 2023; Hussain, 2025c for the
837 rich evidence available for this on the structure of Palaeolithic mobile and parietal art). This
838 would not only resonate with the often-overriding performative emphasis on animal body
839 partiality discussed in the previous section, it would also align with other key features of the
840 respective visual worlds themselves: radical embeddedness, pictorial incompleteness, and
841 differences in highlighting different animal gestures and body parts in different periods. Again,
842 the Linnean gaze and its underlying ontology of privileging organismal “appearance” and
843 “wholeness” could well lead us fundamentally astray. The significance of the visual and the
844 logic of the Palaeolithic gaze may thus uncomfortably confront our own “ways of seeing”
845 (Berger, 1972), and how we visually render and thereby enact our *own* worlds.

846 The representational status of Palaeolithic zoovisuality is also challenged on other
847 frontiers and by other archaeological observations. Based on detailed contextual and
848 technological analyses, it has for example been argued that the remarkable assemblage of burnt
849 zoomorphic clay figurines from the Moravian Pavlovian was probably at least in part
850 fragmented and then buried in place after their fire-aided manufacture and shape imposition
851 (Verpoorte, 2000; Farbstein, 2011). This reconstruction considerably weakens the interpretation
852 of such objects as purposed to be spectated and revisited as “representations” in the traditional
853 understanding of the concept. The empirical evidence rather highlights the *performative*
854 background of these salient instances of zoovisuality. I suggest that contexts such as these
855 should compel us to seriously consider whether visual practice was sometimes less about
856 “depicting” and “representing” something at a distance and instead perhaps concerned with
857 what I would like to call the “presencing” of significant others. In other words, visual practices
858 may have been a cultural technique to close and narrow human-animal distances and to create
859 proximity, rather than producing, and hence reinforcing, such distances. Once “presenced”, the
860 ontological status of animal imagery is not categorically different from the ontological status of
861 living embodied animals, and to render animals visually may thus mean to conjure them, to
862 “make them co-present” (see esp. Bird-David, 2017b, 2017a on the notion of being co-present).
863 To appreciate this, we again need to let go with the (itself ontologically grounded) idea that the
864 abstract rather than the literal is the pinnacle of world-making, and thus to separate discussions
865 of representation from the cognitive evolution of *Homo sapiens*. To deny the ontological
866 collapse of depiction and being is to say that the delineation between image/representation and
867 being/existence is universally valid and unshakable, and imaging something can therefore never
868 be about re-instating being/presence but always points to something other than the image itself,
869 i.e., the image always remains secondary – it exhibits derived, and not primary, existence. Such
870 insistence would not only reveal ontological dogma and Westerncentrism, it is also challenged
871 by anthropological accounts suggesting that practices of presencing may be key for the

horse populations, suggesting that cave paintings of this species represent remarkably realistic depictions of the animals shown. This finding lends support to hypotheses arguing that cave paintings might have contained less of a symbolic or transcendental connotation than often assumed.”

872 functioning and reproduction of many, so-called “pluripresent” Indigenous socialities around
873 the world (Bird-David, 2017b; Descola, 2021).

874 This ontological critique of the Palaeolithic image, I propose, can open up novel,
875 exciting avenues for understanding and comparing the diversity of visual cultures in the deep
876 past. Rather than interrogating zoovisuality *over yonder*, we may wish to ask whether some
877 animals are visualized precisely when they become rarer on the landscape, thus inverting the
878 assumed relationship between depiction and environmental presence, notably because such
879 linkage has also been mobilized to explain unusual practices of animal body treatment, for
880 example cave lion pelt extraction during the Iberian Magdalenian (Marián Cueto *et al.*, 2016).
881 Potential examples from the corpus of European Upper Palaeolithic parietal and mobile art
882 include the seals, mammoths, and rhinos from the Magdalenian of Gönnersdorf (Hansen, 2006;
883 Płonka, 2018), the Bad Kösen wholly rhino from the same period (Richter *et al.*, 2024), the
884 engraving of a giant deer from the end of the Italian Late Glacial (Mussi, 2001), as well as Early
885 Upper Palaeolithic hyena depictions from Chauvet (Baynes-Rock, 2015) or the great auk
886 renderings of Cosquer likely predating the Last Glacial Maximum (d’Errico, 1994). Visual
887 practice in such contexts may be concerned with counteracting animal disappearance and may
888 have thus been employed to compensate for decreasing opportunities of direct engagement and
889 communication. Practices of “presencing”, in other words, may be a hitherto overlooked
890 cultural technique (*sensu* Macho, 2013) to facilitate dialogue and proximity within multispecies
891 communities, to be deployed in particular when confronted with the physical elapse of
892 significant nonhuman others. This may also explain some supposedly late depictions of now-
893 extinct megafaunal species in the Americas, previously interpreted as a “late survival” signature
894 (Iriarte *et al.*, 2022). Taking the ontological critique seriously hence means to allow for plural
895 ontologies of images and image-making practices – an image may not always be the same, and
896 the very notion of the “image” may already overburden some visual pasts.

897

898 **Conclusion: Animality reconsidered**

899 This paper has attempted to take the ontological critique seriously and to delineate some
900 emerging areas of concern in the deep-time archaeology of human-animal relations. I have
901 highlighted the importance of an evidence-driven approach to some of the issues raised by the
902 critique, but coevally cautioned against the tendency to curtail what can count as archaeological
903 observation, data, and credible interpretation in the first place – touching upon the core of what
904 Palaeolithic and Mesolithic archaeologists commonly accept as rehearsed ways of doing
905 science, asking questions, and understanding the past. As a result, I have suggested that the call
906 to engage the ontological is often mischaracterized, or misunderstood, as the emergence of a
907 “new metaphysical” ambition among archaeologists, when it merely seeks to hold open, and
908 enhance, the possibilities for tracing past worlds enacted and understood in radical different
909 terms than the worlds present-day archaeologists inhabit and promulgate. The engagement with
910 ontology, in this view, is an exercise of “breaking up” our own ontological closures and to let
911 the evidence speak in such a way that it can challenge the very positionalities we bring to bear
912 on it. This is the radical empirical impetus of the ontological critique, and I have argued that
913 the empirical opening that it promises, notably long overdue attention to how we *observe* and
914 *describe* the archaeological record with regard to animal questions, can be immensely beneficial
915 to human-animal archaeologies. As I have tried to show, it can help to bring into view radical
916 zooalterities as expressed in the nature, structure, and logics of past human-animal engagements
917 difficult to make sense of by invoking presentist baselines. The overriding challenge may
918 accordingly be to find productive ways of strategically dispensing with the many evidential
919 stereotypes currently underpinning deep-time human-animal studies, and to tap into the
920 archaeological record to distil new, situated categories of analysis and interpretation, with all

921 the challenges and risks that such an endeavour implies. I have suggested that being acutely
922 attentive to how humans have engaged with zoomaterialities in the past as well as what kind of
923 zoovisualities they have authored, and in what broader multispecies context, helps to identify
924 dead ends and conceptual impasses of conventional research perspectives, to challenge a whole
925 range of entrenched Western assumptions, and to rework our conceptual registers to better
926 account for the weirdness (in contrast to WEIRD-ness) of the deep past. This must include
927 resisting the temptation to reify ontological systems such as “animism”, “perspectivism”,
928 “totemism”, “analogism” and “naturalism” as newfound metaphysical orthodoxy, and it must
929 equally withstand the temptation to domesticate the past with Indigenous ontologies. This is a
930 difficult undertaking and requires the cultivation of ontological literacy as well as the careful
931 engagement with debates on anthropological and zoological difference, but – as I have
932 attempted to demonstrate with a range of archaeological examples sourced from various
933 Pleistocene and Holocene hunter-gatherer contexts – the critical analysis of key concepts such
934 as “function” and “representation” and their confrontation with data pertaining to human-
935 animal relationships can be instrumental for working towards such animal archaeologies,
936 recognizing that ontology ought not to be an input category but a target outcome of analysis.
937 We should be careful, in other words, not to confuse ontological animal archaeologies with the
938 sort of “political ontology” Blaser (2013) has called for in anthropology.

939 Acceptance of the overarching ambition of ontological human-animal archaeologies to
940 reveal rather than precast diverse, potentially unfamiliar “zoo-ontologies” also implies that we
941 must be prepared to destabilize the category of the “animal” itself – both “animal” and “human”
942 are situated discursive and world-making products, they presuppose and co-define each other,
943 and they stand for but one way of negotiating and affirm difference (Hussain, 2025a). As Wolfe
944 (2003) reminds us, the “animal” has historically functioned as a constitutive other in Western
945 thought, conducive to its achievements as well as its harms. Animality is thus only the flipside
946 of the kind of humanity currently conceived (Armstrong Oma, 2018), and it is a crucial task of
947 ontological human-animal archaeologies to devise approaches to the archaeological record
948 which enable us to ask how other societies sorted through the nonhuman world, categorized,
949 and hierarchized nonhuman others, or not, and therefore what significance the human-animal
950 asymmetry (Derrida, 2010) holds in comparative perspective. The “animal” must consequently
951 receive the same critical attention as concepts such as “function” and “representation”, and it is
952 here that animal archaeologies can perhaps make particularly important contributions to broader
953 multispecies studies and the anthropology of othering. This is because such “zoo-ontological”
954 archaeologies ultimately bring into view alternative ways of being human.

955

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961

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966

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